

THE SCIENTIFIC ACTIVITY OF Y.E.BERTELS IS AN ORIENTALIST.

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Annotation: *In this article, East people's history, culture, language of the great specialist Y.E.Bertels life and work, essence of his scientific activity are revealed. At the same time, the article talks about the contribution of the great thinker Jami's scientific heritage of learning*

Keywords: *Y.E.Bertels, Jami, Persian language and literature, classic, modern literature, orientalist, Alisher Navai*

Academician Yevgeniy Eduardovich Bertels' scientific creative work is characterized with Turkish, Persian-Tajik, Sufism literature and different topics. He is considered a great scientist who has done remarkable work on the spiritual heritage of the Eastern thinkers and the history of their culture. The direction of scientist's research is very broad, in his works, the general view and interaction of Persian-Tajik and Turkish philology are comparatively investigated. The orientalist Y.E.Bertels' scientific work of studying history of Sufism, philosophy and literature covers all aspects of everyday life. It is emphasized, the studying of Jami's life and work was considered one of the main topics in the scientist's scientific research.

Before Y.E.Bertels, any scientist covered such an important topic in his scientific work. Orientalist Abdurahman Jami compared his works with examples of artistic creations before him and expressed his conclusions. Orientalist Yevgeny Eduardovich Bertels (December 25, 1890 St Petersburg, October 7, 1957, Moscow) graduated from the Imperial University of St Petersburg (1914) and entered the law department. In 1918 he was a student of Petrograd conservatory (later Leningrad) State University, which was taught Persian and Turkish languages. A.A.Ramaskevich, A.A.Freiman, V.Bartold and S.Oldenburger were mentors of Y.E.Bertels. A year later, he was appointed a teacher of Persian language and literature at the Institute of Oriental Languages in Petrograd (later the Leningrad Oriental Institute which was named after A.S.Enukidze), and in 1928 he was appointed a professor of Persian language and literature at the Leningrad State University for Barthold's recommendation.

In 1932 he was appointed head of the History and Linguistics department of the Tajik branch of the Academy of Sciences of the Soviet Union in Leningrad (while maintaining other academic duties) and in 1939 he was appointed a correspondent member of the Academy of Sciences of the Soviet Union .In 1942 Y.E.Bertels was urgently transferred from Leningrad to Tashkent with the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy Sciences of the Former Soviet Union. At first, he worked as researcher at the Institute of Language and Literature of the Academy of Sciences , then he was as a professor at the present UzMU. In 1946 Y.E.Bertels moved to Moscow. Y.E.Bertels devoted his whole life to study and embody classical and modern Persian and Tajik poetry in his work ,combining with language, philosophy , literature and music theory of Iran. [1,69b]

Y.E.Bertels was one of the first oriental studies in the world, he compared and analyzed the” Khamsa” of Nizami Ganjavi, Alisher Navai, Amir Khusrav, Abdurahman Jami and revealed their achievements and shortcomings of the basic of irrefutable scientific facts. As noted by N.Komilov ,who is a mystic and scientist ,the field of research is very wide, “Y.E.Bertels objectively revealed friendship between Navai and Jami , the literary environment of Herat and the content of Navai’s works”[2,202b] Y.E.Bertels believes that when studying the work of each author , it is necessary firstly to focus on the important aspects of the subject. Cultural and spiritual factors play an important role in creativity play an important role in the formation of any talent. Y.E.Bertels conducted a number of studies on Jami’s work .His legacy was scientifically introduced to Russian science by Y.E.Bertels but the Russian scientist A.A.Lukashav’s opinion , the ideas advanced in Y.E.Bertels translations require revision . Because the works that ensure the scientific proportionality of the translated works have appeared recently.[3,118b]

It was the study and analysis of Navoi’s work that motivated Y.E.Bertels to study the scientific heritage of his teacher Jami. The scientists study of Navai’s work will serve as an important object for future studies. Y.E.Bertels showed the highest peak of the culture of two brotherly peoples in the works of Jami and Navai. In the comparative study of Persian literature Y.E.Bertels did not limit himself to the comparasion of work of Turkish speaking authors , but studied with poetic images , metaphors and styles. We call it Y.E.Bertels can observe it in all works of Bertels dedicated to Jami’s work [4,7]

Academician Y.E.Bertels scientific research on the life and work of the great Persian –Tajik poet Abdurahman Jami is one of the studies that does not lost their

importance even today. Very little is written about Jami in Russian . Jami is mentioned only in some articles of M.A.Sale . This in essence could not cover the great creativity of the poet. Information about Jami’s life and work in European literature is included in the foreword written by Nassau Lees to the work “Nafohat al –uns “(Breezes of friendship) and in the introduction by A.Masse to the French translation of “Bahoristan”.The information in both articles was recorded by his student Abdulgafur Lori written after Jami’s death. According to Bertels , Iranian scholars have done very little research on Jami. Only Ali Asqar Hikmat published a monograph for high schools in 1942 . However, although the information presented in it has a relatively rich scientific value, not all of it is correct.Apparently, in the period before Bertels , Eastern and Western scientists did not pay enough attention to the scientific and spiritual heritage of Jami.

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